

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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ANALYSIS OF TOURISTIC POTENTIAL AND CAPACITY OF ECOTOURISM SITES

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Abstract: Ecotourism has become one of the areas of great interest among world economists. Therefore, several methods are used to study this area. By determining the capacity of ecotourism sites to receive tourists, analyzes were carried out to prevent damage to the ecosystem in the regulation area, its quality decrease, the deterioration of the attractiveness of the ecological environment, and the decrease in its aesthetic value, thereby increasing their economic value.

Key words: Ecotourism, tourists, protected areas, tourist capacity, acceptable capacity, potential capacity, basic capacity.

Annotatsiya: Ekoturizm dunyo iqtisodchilari orasida katta qiziqish uyg'otayotgan yo'nalishlardan biriga aylangan. Shu sababli bu sohani o'rganishda bir nechta usullardan foydalaniladi. Ekoturizm obyektlarining sayyohlarni qabul qilish salohiyati aniqlanib, ularning iqtisodiy qiymatini oshirish maqsadida ekotizimga zarar yetkazilishining, ekologik hududning jozibadorligi va estetik qiymatining kamayishining oldini olish bo'yicha tahlillar o'tkazildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ekoturizm, sayyohlar, muhofaza etiladigan hududlar, sayyohlar sig'imi, qabul qilinadigan sig'im, potensial sig'im, asosiy sig'im.

Аннотация: Экотуризм стал одним из направлений, вызывающих большой интерес среди мировых экономистов. В связи с этим используются различные методы для его изучения. Определив туристическую ёмкость экотуристических объектов, были проведены анализы, направленные на предотвращение ущерба экосистеме, снижение качества и привлекательности экологической среды, а также её эстетической ценности, что, в свою очередь, способствует повышению экономической ценности таких территорий.

Ключевые слова: Экотуризм, туристы, охраняемые территории, туристическая ёмкость, допустимая ёмкость, потенциальная ёмкость, базовая ёмкость.

INTRODUCTION

Ecotourists can cause various negative effects on the environment, because increased human intervention in ecological areas leads to irreversible changes in existing ecological processes. These include the depletion of natural resources, the expansion of plant populations and habitats, deforestation, and the reduction of high water flows. A large number of tourists causes damage to the ecological system in ecotourism zones, leading to a decline in environmental quality, increased noise and pollution, and reduced aesthetic value and attractiveness of the ecotourism environment.

As a result of global environmental challenges such as climate change and biodiversity loss, interest in ecotourism is growing. Ecotourism offers new opportunities for the development of the tourism industry and

job creation, while minimizing its harmful impact on the environment. Ecotourism is a rapidly growing niche market within one of the world's largest industries (Rosaleen Duffy, 2006). The global ecotourism market size is expected to have increased by 13.5% to \$249.16 billion in 2024, up from \$219.53 billion in 2023, and is projected to reach \$428.97 billion in 2028.

The potential of ecotourism to contribute to poverty reduction and local socio-economic development has been emphasized by many scholars (Mitchell and Ashley, 2010; Spenceley, 2008b) and organizations such as the World Bank, UNWTO, and WTTC. Ecotourism contributes to the development of related industries such as restaurants and transport (Linsheng Z., Buckley R. & Ting X., 2007). It also creates jobs in roles such as porters, taxi drivers, translators, and tourist guides (Hunt C. A., William H. D., Laura D., and Martha H., 2015; Khanal L., 2019).

Beyond direct employment, ecotourism fosters the development of essential infrastructure, including buildings, roads, parks, hotels, and airports. These investments generate additional jobs beyond the service and hospitality sectors (Mitchell J. & Ashley C., 2010). Roe and Elliott found that ecotourism allows poor communities to utilize natural resources in diverse ways that support livelihood diversification, such as trading in wood or wild fruits, producing crafts, and engaging in formal or informal employment (Roe D. and Elliott J., 2006). In this context, ecotourism is positively associated with job creation, small business development, and poverty alleviation.

Ecotourism has substantial potential to support global efforts against poverty. A study initiated by the WTO concluded that in developing countries, especially in the least developed nations, tourism is nearly always the leading driver of economic growth, foreign exchange earnings, investment, and employment ([ICIMOD]). Interaction between tourists and poor local communities through ecotourism holds immense promise for improving political, economic, social, and cultural conditions in those communities (Jones and Lalley, 2013).

There are different approaches, trends, and perspectives on assessing the standard of living of the population. These are often based on the general characteristics of the subject under study. Overall, it is observed that living standards are improving in many areas. However, global development experience shows that economic growth does not always yield positive social outcomes. This is evident in the unequal creation of favorable conditions for raising education levels and access to healthcare, cultural and sports participation, and mitigating unemployment risks.

Therefore, a system of indicators assessing living standards has gradually evolved, incorporating demographic and socio-economic measures. These indicators reflect multiple dimensions of human development. Methodologies for calculating them have been refined, and international classifications have been developed (F.B. Tursunov, 2022).

Experts have used varying criteria to assess living standards. In many cases, recurring criteria reflect the general socio-economic conditions. These include quantitative indicators used for objective assessment, such as the level and dynamics of food and commodity prices, basic goods affordability, per capita income, tax and social payment burdens, and the percentage of the population living below the poverty line (F.B. Tursunov, 2022).

Unlike prior studies, this research also analyzes the role of ecotourism in employment, alongside infrastructure development and overall employment levels. It centers on a key question: to what extent does ecotourism contribute to the socio-economic upliftment of local communities in Samarkand? Applying a mixed-methods approach, the study systematically examines the complex interaction between ecotourism initiatives and local economic outcomes particularly in terms of employment, income levels, and rural infrastructure development.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

In summarising the literature, De Witt et al. (2011, p. 1139) suggest that the key principles of ecotourism are that it should foster a genuine interest in nature, contribute to conservation, respect and conserve local culture, make non-consumptive use of natural resources, yield benefits to the local community and create tourist awareness of conservation and local community issues. Based on this definition, ecotourism in this paper is taken to include activities which are nature- and culture-based, sustainable, promote conservation and provide benefits to local people in the area. Since many of the impacts, costs and benefits of tourism are the same as those for ecotourism in the study areas, the two terms are used synonymously throughout the paper.

Tourism has commonly been regarded as a mechanism for improving the livelihoods of local people in destinations. Particularly the potential of tourism for the generation of employment and income for locals has been one of the main reasons for the adoption of tourism. Tourism may also be useful for other purposes such as reducing out migration; in the case of some countries, for example, tourism has been adopted to provide

more rural employment with special emphasis on the needs of the young population who form the bulk of out-migrants (Murphy, 1985). So significant are the role and contribution of tourism to employment that it may arguably be described as the world's largest source of employment in the world (Sharpley & Telfer, 2002), in both developed and developing countries.

A.Nigmatova, N. Shomurotova's book "Fundamentals of Ecotourism" was created for those who study ecotourism and work in the field of ecotourism from a practical point of view, the requirements and recommendations of ecotourism, ecotourism zoning of the territory of Uzbekistan.

Previous research frequently argued that ecotourism is a component of the green economy and has a significant role in natural resource protection (Anup, K. (2015)). It is believed that employment in ecotourism operations enhances people's awareness of the importance of conservation (Hunt C. A (2015), Shibia (2010), Snyman, S. (2014)) , and local people generally hold positive attitudes toward the environment in the protected areas (Mehta, J. N (2010), Snyman, S. (2014), Tessema, M. E (2007)). Therefore, ecotourism is spurred as a strategy to promote local people's involvement in conservation activities. Also, ecotourism development is considered a solution to stem the activities that undermine conservation, such as forest degradation, expanding agricultural frontiers, illegal hunting, logging, firewood collection, and uncontrolled burning (Muchapondwa, E. (2003)).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

According to the World Tourism Organization, "Maximum capacity of tourism" means "at the same time it is possible to visit a tourist destination without harming the physical, economic, socio-cultural environment and without causing an unacceptable decrease in the quality of tourism" is defined as the maximum number of people" (Tukhliyev I.S. 2014). Middleton and Hawkins Chamberlain defined it as "the level of human activity that can be accommodated in an area without degrading the area, adversely affecting the resident community, or reducing visitor numbers" (Bell, Frederick, and Vernon Leeworthy. 1990). Maximum capacity is the point at which a facility or attraction begins to experience discomfort due to the number of visitors.

There are several different forms of maximum capacity in tourism, including:

1. Maximum physical capacity. This is the maximum number of tourists that the region can actually accommodate. Usually this is considered to be around 1 m² per person. "Physical maximum capacity per day (PCC) = area (m²) x visitor area (m²) x daily activity duration (hours)" (Bell, Frederick, and Vernon Leeworthy. 1990).

2. Economic maximum capacity. This refers to the level of acceptable changes in the local economy of the tourist destination, the ability of this tourist destination to establish touristic functions without losing local activity, and the places allocated for business activities are also taken into account in this indicator. Economic maximum capacity can also be used to describe the point at which revenues from tourism development are outpaced by tourism-induced inflation.

3. Maximum social capacity. This is related to the negative socio-cultural effects associated with the development of tourism. Indicators of when social maximum capacity has been exceeded, as described in the Doxey index, is a decline in the local population's acceptance of tourism in the area. Decreased visitor enjoyment and increased crime are also indicators of increased social capacity.

4. Biophysical maximum capacity. It depends on how well the natural environment can withstand the interference of tourists. Some ecological resources are renewable, but if their maximum capacity exceeds the capacity of the habitat to regenerate, it will cause great damage. Maximum environmental capacity also applies to ecological and physical parameters, resources, ecosystems and infrastructure capacity.

One of the weaknesses of determining maximum capacity is that, on a practical level, it is difficult to estimate the maximum number of visitors, as it also depends on the behavior of tourists.

Samarkand region is very famous in the world through cultural tourism. But Samarkand also has a huge ecotourism potential. Sitara-bonu Sadikova and Sabine Hennig considered it appropriate to identify the following aspects:

- types of recreation in the lap of nature (active, passive relaxations, health healing & meditation, scientific research, etc.);
- popular active type of rest in the Samarkand Region natural areas (hiking, skiing, bacycling, swimming, climbing, etc.);
- overage duration of rest of the local people in the natural areas;
- concretization by matching popular vocation spots on a map (Sitara-bonu Sadikova and Sabine Hennig 2020) (Table 1).

Table 1. Some ecotourism places in Samarkand region

№	Name of ecotourism facilities	Location address	Area (ha)	Distance from the regional center (km)	Specialized services	Number of workers
1.	Zarafshan National Park	Jomboy district	2426,4	20	Specialists providing information on zoology and botany	35
2.	Ertaklar olami	Ishtikhan district	47	64,9	Fishing	20
3.	Teshiktosh	Urgut district	1	76,4	Watching the mountain and the thousand-year-old stone	4
4.	Ming archa	Urgut district	50	39,6	Spruce garden and catering service	23
5.	Oqboyro	Samarkand district	30	9,4	Water pool and special recreational activities	94
6.	Hazrati Dovud	Nurobod district	28	42,7	Mountainside trip	14

Today, ecological excursions in Uzbekistan, the Samarkand region are very interesting for tourists, especially trips to the Zarafshan national park. In this natural complex, flooded tugai forests and shrub thickets disappearing due to regulation of river flow, which retain some features of the flora of the Tertiary period, are presented. You can find sea-buckthorn, oleaster, willow, tamarisk, walnut and grapes in the Zarafshan National park. Part of the vegetation has remained since the times when fruit gardens were planted in the area of the present reserve (A.Abdurakhmanova 2023).

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Assessment of the suitability of the place for ecotourism requires the collection and study of information in order to optimally organize and manage the ecotourism area according to its suitability, minimize the impact of ecotourism activities and create rehabilitation efficiency, conservation, protection and conservation of natural resources. , in addition, effective planning and development policies are needed to realize the capacity determination of the facility.

Ecotourist carrying capacity is a useful concept in wildlife management and determines how many ecotourists can visit an ecotourism area.

The assessment of tourist capacity in tourism is based on the method proposed by Cifuentes in 1992, in which tourist capacity is based on the area of activity, as well as the period of tourism activity in each destination (Table 2).

Table 2. Standard areas for ecotourism services

№	Types of ecotourism services	Standard area for 1 person (m ²)
1.	Swimming	100
2.	Beach	50
3.	Take a walk	1000
4.	Waterfall	50
5.	Cave	20
6.	Learning about culture	25
7.	Fishing	50

You can see from the table above that for 1 person 100 m² for swimming, 50 m² for relaxing on beaches or seaside, 30 m² for hiking or special things (plant study, animal watching, waterfall viewing 50 m², 20 m² for exploring caves, 25 m² for cultural history, 50 m² for fishing.

In general, there are four steps to calculate tourist capacity. To use this method, it is important to take into account tourist flows, the size of the territory, the optimal space available for free movement of each tourist, and the time of visit. In the course of our research, we have calculated the maximum capacity of tourists who can visit "Zarafshan National Park". This research method is briefly described in Figure 1 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The basis of the tourism capacity method

The following indicators are important for receiving tourists of the ecotourism area:

1. Standard area requirement for activity. There is a standard area requirement for certain tourism activities. The standard area is based on the need of the environment for certain types of activities, including tourism activities. A special equation for each tourism activity is used to calculate the standard area

2. Space for each activity. Each activity area is the actual area (m²) for the implementation of tourist activities in each direction. In addition, the information comes from direct observations in all directions.

3. Average time for activity. Average available time for movement is the average number of hours per day that each route is served. This information is based on the duration conditions of each tourist activity.

4. Average visit time. Average visit time is the average time (hours) it takes to complete each activity. It is also based on direct observation of how long tourists spend on specific activities in each destination. Bularni aniqlashda quyidagi ko'rsatkichlardan foydalaniladi.

Rotation coefficient (RC). RC is a coefficient that compares the average tourist time for the implementation of tourist activities with the available time for the implementation of tourist activities per day.

$$RC = \frac{\text{Time available for activity}}{\text{average visit time}} \quad (5)$$

Limiting factor 1: coefficient of duration of activity during the year (Lf1). Occurred due to seasonality throughout the year.

$$Lf1 = \frac{(100 - ((\text{bad weather days} \div 365) \times 100))}{100} \quad (6)$$

Limiting factor 2: Coefficient of duration of daily activity (Lf2)

Coefficient that takes into account the operating time per day of the destination

$$Lf2 = \frac{(100 - ((\text{operating hours} \div 24) \times 100))}{100} \quad (7)$$

Basic maximum capacity (BCC). BCC is a comparison of an area with standard area requirements for tourist-defined activities.

$$BCC = \frac{\text{A space for each activity}}{\text{Default field}} \quad (8)$$

Potential maximum capacity (PCC). PCC is the value of the ability to receive potential tourists in a certain area, regardless of the time of operation. When calculating PCC, the RC coefficient and the result of BCC are taken into account.

$$PCC = BCC \times RC \quad (9)$$

Actual Maximum Capacity (RCC)

RCC is the actual value of the tourist assessment. RCC also includes a PCC value that takes into account operational time such as overtime and bad weather conditions. The value of RCC reflects the maximum number of tourists allowed from the designated area to carry out the activity. RCC value can be calculated for one day or one year.

$$RCC = PCC \times Lf1 \times Lf2 \quad (10)$$

From the time of establishment in “Zarafshan National Park” until now, only services such as watching animals, feeding, studying plants, and taking a walk in a scenic area have been offered. Based on the ecoroutes established in “Zarafshan National Park”, the number of tourists who came to the park was studied (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Tourists who visited “Zarafshan National Park” in 2019-2021

The distribution of income from these ecotourists is as follows (Table 3):

Table 3. Funds received from ecotourists who visited Zarafshan National Park in 2019-2021 (thousand soums)

№	Visitors	2019	2020	2021	Change in 2021 compared to 2019	
1	Pupils and students	1175	2650	5088,87	3913,87	increased by 4.3 times
2	Individuals and legal entities	2005	1932	19139,5	17134,5	increased 9.5 times
	Total	3180	4582	24228,37	21048,37	7.6 times increased

From the data in the table, we can see that in 2021, due to the increase in the number of ecotourists, we can see that the income from tourists increased by 7.61 times compared to 2019. The main reason for the decrease in ecotourists in 2020 is the worldwide spread of the COVID-2019 virus. Due to the quarantine measures caused by this disease, access to the park was closed, which in turn led to a decrease in the number of visitors and a decrease in income. This income is mainly used to stay in METH, as stated in paragraph 3 of the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 13 of January 8, 2018 «On some issues of regulation of stay in protected natural areas». The payment is made in the amount of 5% of the basic calculation per day for each visitor. In addition, agriculture is another source of income in Zarafshan National Park. The park has a total of 302 hectares of land for agricultural activities, and the area used for agriculture is 2117.9 hectares in 2021. million Soum income was received.

That's why we analyze hiking and sightseeing in Zarafshan National Park by type of service. Table 3 below calculates the circulation coefficient to determine the maximum capacity of tourists in Zarafshan National Park (Table 4).

Table 4. Calculation of rotation coefficient (RC) for "Zarafshan National Park"

No	Types of tourist services	Time available for daily activities	Average travel time (hours)	Rotation coefficient (RC)
1.	Walking, sightseeing	8	3	2,66

According to the table, the daily working hours of "Zarafshan National Park" are 8 hours, and the average stay of 1 tourist in the park is 3 hours. Based on this, the turnover ratio for the tourist reception capacity was 2.66.

The limiting factor (Lf1 and Lf2) is a coefficient that takes into account bad weather and operating hours per year in each tourist activity. Limiting factor 1 (Lf1) takes into account the number of days of unfavorable weather in a year. Limiting factor 2 (Lf2) takes into account working hours in one day (Table 5).

Table 5. Analysis of limiting factors (Lf1 and Lf2) for "Zarafshan National Park"

No	Types of tourist services	Unity	Lf1	Lf2
			Bad weather Day/year	Activity Hour/day
1	Walking, sightseeing	Number of days/hours	120	8
		Notes	4 oy	8 ⁰⁰ from 16 ⁰⁰ to
		Coefficient	0,671	0,666

From the data in the table, we can see that the seasonality in "Zarafshan National Park" lasts 4 months, that is, 120 days. Accordingly, the 1st limiting factor was 0.671. One of the elements of the 2nd limiting factor is that the operating hours in "Zarafshan National Park" are 8 hours. Based on this, the result of limiting factor 2 gave 0.666. Based on the two limiting factor accounting books, it can be used as a key indicator to calculate the actual tourist reception capacity (RCC). The calculation of RCC is based on the area (hectares) for a specific tourism activity, as shown in Table 1. Table 2.17 summarizes all calculations using the equations described above. The result of the calculation is the RCC calculation, which is a number that reflects the maximum number of tourists (people) that can visit each area for a certain tourist activity (Table 6).

Table 6. The capacity of "Zarafshan National Park" to receive tourists throughout the year

Type of service	Walking and sightseeing
Area reserved for ecotourism (m2)	3524000
Standard area for activity (m2)	1000
Rotation coefficient	2,66
Limiting factor 1 (Lf1)	0,671
Limiting factor 2 (Lf2)	0,666
The main tourist reception capacity (person/day)	3524
Potential tourist capacity (person/day)	9373
Actual tourist reception capacity (person/day)	4189
Actual tourist reception capacity (person/year)	1026314

According to Table 5, the area of the recreation department in "Zarafshan National Park" is 352.4 hectares (3524000 m²). Ecotourism routes are organized in this area. Based on the above formulas, the main capacity of the park to receive tourists is 3524 people per day, the potential capacity is 9373 people, the actual capacity is 4189 people per day, and the actual capacity is 1026314 people per year.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This RCC is a real example that explains the overall tourism carrying capacity of the environment, which can support tourism activities without adversely affecting it. RCC is a number assigned to all visitors entering a

specific area of tourism activity. Thus, this number includes residents, traders, tourism-related people, as well as all people included in these areas.

By determining the capacity of ecotourism sites to receive tourists, the regulation helps to prevent damage to the ecosystem in the area, a decrease in its quality, a decrease in the attractiveness of the ecological environment, and a decrease in its aesthetic value, thereby increasing their economic value.

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IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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